

Franziska Altemeier

TIB LEIBNIZ-INFORMATIONSZENTRUM
TECHNIK UND NATURWISSENSCHAFTEN
UNIVERSITÄTSBIBLIOTHEK

Juliane Jacob

UH
Universität Hamburg
DER FORSCHUNG | DER LEHRE | DER BILDUNG

Jorge Murcia Serra

UB
UNIVERSITY LIBRARY
MANNHEIM

BERD
@NFDI

DATA LITERACY IN FOCUS: USING THE LEARNING OBJECTIVES MATRIX TO TEACH RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

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AGENDA

- Teaching RDM in Academic Libraries
- The Learning Objective Matrix for RDM-Training
- Use Cases
- Conclusions

TEACHING RDM IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

TEACHING RDM IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

Research Data Management (RDM)

A definition of RDM:

*“a number of different activities and processes associated with the data lifecycle, involving the **design and creation of data, storage, security, preservation, retrieval, sharing, and reuse**, all taking into account technical capabilities, ethical considerations, legal issues and governance frameworks”*

(Andrew M. Cox & Stephen Pinfield, 2013)

TEACHING RDM IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

RDM in Academic Libraries – Services

- location and acquisition of data
- analysis, publishing, handling, and management of metadata
- data preservation (including institutional repositories)
- consultations in legal and ethical aspects of research data
- establishment of data management plans
- **Training in RDM**

TEACHING RDM IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

Key Academic Literacies taught in Libraries

- Information Literacy
- Digital Literacy
- Data Literacy
- **Research Data Management**

TEACHING RDM IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

Why?

- Collection, analysis and presentation of data are core competences for researchers

BUT

- Storage of data, security issues, data integrity, long-term preservation, sharing for reuse (metadata!) generally have not been up to now part of academic curricula

SO TAKE

- Expertise at academic libraries in acquiring, organizing, managing, and preserving large volumes of data, along with proficiency in handling metadata and persistent identifiers

AND

- Experience in training on information, digital and data literacy

YOU GET: Training on RDM in Academic Libraries

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

A bit of history

- 2022: [First version](#) (German)
- 2023: [Second version](#) (German / English)
- 2024 - 2025 [Third version](#)
 - Community-Event in Darmstadt, Germany 2024
 - Integration through editorial team followed by Call4Comments
 - Final version published in March 2025
 - English version in September 2025

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

Learning Objectives ...

- ... describe the intended learning outcome in relation to a specific subject
- ... help learners to manage the learning process effectively
- ... are helpful in planning teaching and learning scenarios

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

Formulating Learning Objectives (Bloom's Taxonomy)

- Learning objectives should be verifiably
~~“learners know the criteria...”~~ > “learners can name the criteria...”
- Learning objectives should be clearly and precisely formulated
*~~“learners can name principles for sustainable research data practices”~~ >
“learners can name the FAIR principles”*
- Learning objectives should be operationalized in such a way that learning success can be achievable, measurable and thus evaluable
*~~know, understand, recognize, be familiar with, be informed~~ >
name, explain, apply, analyze, assess, design*

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

Formulating Learning Objectives (Bloom's Taxonomy)

- **Learning objective start:** Containing personal anchor [learners are able to]
- **Action component/ verb:** describing the activity the learner should be able to accomplish to fulfil the learning objective [apply]
- **Content component:** provides information about the specific skill to be acquired [methods for data documentation]
- **(Conditions):** By adding conditions under which observable behavior should take place, LO can be refined and tailored to an individual didactic scenario [independently]

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

What is the Learning Objective Matrix for RDM-Training?

- The LOM summarizes relevant teaching content as well as learning objectives in a uniform form for different learning levels (Bachelor's students, Master's students, Early Career Researcher and Data Steward),
- It is a continuously developing product of the FDM (training) community,
- It follows a generic approach and thus enables application and adaptation across disciplinary and organizational boundaries.

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

Target groups

- RDM disseminators or faculty teaching staff applying the matrix to their contexts, such as:
 - RDM Information Events
 - RDM training
 - Integration of RDM topics into courses and curricula

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

Subjects included

- Fundamental and comprehensive concepts (201)
- Working with data (396)
- Documentation and metadata (203)
- Archiving, publication, reuse (98)
- Law and ethics (202)
- Meta-Competences (99)

THE LEARNING OBJECTIVE MATRIX FOR RDM-TRAINING

Some examples

Start	Verb	Content
Learners are able to	name	the FAIR principles.
Learners are able to	evaluate	the interoperability of non-proprietary file formats.
Learners are able to	apply	methods for data documentation independently.
Learners are able to	analyse	challenges for the long-term usability of data.
Learners are able to	explain	the characteristics of open and restricted licences.
Learners are able to	design	didactic methods.

USE CASES

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Adaptation for a specific subject or target group

The LOM can be used to identify relevant topics on RDM for a specific subject (e. g. Humanities or Social Sciences) to develop suitable courses or training material.

The LOM helps to tailor RDM training for a specific target group (e. g. BA or MA students)

USE CASES

Self-study and skills development

The LOM helps to identify gaps in one's own RDM-skills and define the need for further training.

The LOM can be used to identify relevant topics for professional RDM-development and training of library staff.

CONCLUSIONS

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Take aways

- The LOM offers an extremely valuable foundation for academic libraries planning to offer or in need to further develop training programs on RDM.
- With the LOM, academic libraries have the possibility of tailoring teaching offers for different target groups in accordance with the current requirements of the faculties and departments on campus.
- The LOM offers a basis for designing didactic scenarios and formulating training outputs in such a way, that their achievement can be verified.
- The LOM is an ideal contribution to quality management for libraries to better evaluate their teaching programmes on RDM.

LINKS UND QUELLEN

Come to the Matrix

- Petersen, B. et al. (2025). Learning Objectives Matrix on the Topic of Research Data Management (RDM) [Working paper]. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15846806>

ANY QUESTION?

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